

The Effect of Organizational Change, Adaptive Leadership, and Role Clarity on the Performance of Syiah Kuala University Employees with Work Stress as A Mediation Variable

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to examine the influence of organizational change, adaptive leadership, and role clarity on employee performance at Syiah Kuala University, with work stress serving as a mediating variable. The population consisted of all Education Personnel with the status of State Civil Apparatus at Syiah Kuala University, totaling 578 individuals. The sample was selected using a census technique, whereby the entire population was included as the sample. Data analysis was conducted using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). The results indicated that organizational change, adaptive leadership, role clarity, work stress, and employee performance at Syiah Kuala University were at satisfactory levels. Furthermore, organizational change, adaptive leadership, and role clarity significantly influenced work stress. Adaptive leadership, role clarity, and work stress, in turn, significantly affected employee performance. Additionally, work stress partially mediated the effects of organizational change, adaptive leadership, and role clarity on employee performance.

KEYWORDS: Organizational Change, Adaptive Leadership, Role Clarity, Job Stress, Employee Performance

1. INTRODUCTION

Syiah Kuala University (USK) is a state university that plays a strategic role in human resource development, science, and social progress in Aceh Province. Since its establishment in 1961, USK has continuously strived to enhance the quality of higher education by strengthening the Tri Dharma of Higher Education, improving academic services, and developing professional institutional governance. USK's vision, as a leading and independent university rooted in Acehese religious and cultural values, demands an adaptive, accountable, and performance-oriented organizational system.

In accordance with the evolving national higher education policy, Syiah Kuala University was officially designated as a State University with Legal Entity status (PTN-BH) through Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 38 of 2022. This designation brings fundamental changes to university governance, particularly by granting increased autonomy in academic, financial, and human resource management. The PTN-BH status provides the university with the flexibility to independently develop strategic policies, establish broader collaborations, and manage resources more efficiently and effectively.

Within the framework of PTN-BH, USK is required to implement a governance system that upholds the principles of accountability, transparency, and sustainable quality assurance. The university's organizational structure is clearly defined through the roles of key bodies such as the Board of Trustees, the University Academic Senate, and the Rector. This system demands professionalism and optimal performance from all members of the organization, particularly employees, who are the primary implementers of the institution's policies and operations.

The institutional transformation from a regular state university to a legal entity (PTN-BH) has significant implications for work patterns and organizational culture. The previously centralized management system has shifted to a more decentralized model, with many strategic decisions now made at the university level. Additionally, changes have been implemented in financial management, recruitment processes, career development, and the adoption of a performance-based remuneration system. These changes are expected to enhance productivity and employee well-being; however, they also demand a high level of adaptability from all staff members.

Employee performance is a critical factor in determining organizational success, including within the context of higher education. At Syiah Kuala University, employee performance is measured through Employee Performance Targets (SKP), which are developed and periodically evaluated in accordance with national regulations. The SKP assessment results indicate that the performance of USK employees generally falls within the good to excellent range. However, a small number of employees continue to demonstrate low performance, necessitating special attention through ongoing coaching and mentoring.

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The results of a pre-survey on employee performance indicate that, while overall performance is considered good, several areas still require improvement, particularly in leadership supervision and oversight of employee performance. Weak supervision can reduce the clarity of work instructions, diminish the effectiveness of feedback, and impede efforts to continuously enhance performance. This situation highlights the significant influence of managerial roles on employee performance, especially during periods of organizational transition.

In addition to affecting performance, organizational change also impacts employees' psychological well-being, notably through the emergence of work-related stress. Work stress can result from increased performance demands, role ambiguity, changes in work systems, and pressure to adapt to new policies. Pre-survey results indicate that employee stress levels at Syiah Kuala University are relatively high. If not properly managed, work stress can reduce employee motivation, concentration, and productivity, ultimately hindering the effectiveness of ongoing organizational changes.

On the other hand, organizational changes at USK are generally perceived to be progressing well, particularly regarding structural and policy adjustments. However, pre-survey results indicate that employees have not yet fully experienced the benefits of these changes in terms of work technology usage. Technological support is a critical factor in enhancing work efficiency and service quality at universities. An imbalance between structural changes and technological improvements can diminish employee performance effectiveness.

Another factor influencing employee performance during organizational change is adaptive leadership. Adaptive leadership highlights a leader's ability to adjust their leadership style to align with environmental dynamics and organizational needs. During the transition to PTN-BH, leaders must provide clear direction, support employees throughout the adaptation process, and foster a conducive work environment. Pre-survey results indicate that adaptive leadership at USK is rated as good; however, there are still weaknesses in leaders' ability to inspire and motivate employees.

In addition to leadership, role clarity is a critical factor influencing employee performance. Role clarity enables employees to understand their duties, responsibilities, and organizational expectations, thereby minimizing confusion and potential workplace conflicts. Pre-survey results indicate that role clarity at Syiah Kuala University is generally satisfactory; however, challenges persist in communication and the clarity of instructions from superiors. Unclear instructions can increase employees' psychological burden and contribute to work-related stress.

A review of previous research indicates that, although numerous studies have examined the influence of leadership on employee performance with work stress as a mediating variable, there is limited research integrating organizational change, adaptive leadership, and role clarity into a single model particularly within the context of state-owned universities. Therefore, this study is both highly relevant and urgent in addressing this research gap.

Based on the description, this study examines the influence of organizational change, adaptive leadership, and role clarity on the performance of employees at Syiah Kuala University, with work stress serving as a mediating variable. The goal is to provide both theoretical and practical contributions to the development of human resource governance and management within the university environment.

2. THEORETICAL STUDY

2.1. Employee Performance

Employee performance fundamentally reflects the level of individual achievement in executing the tasks and responsibilities assigned by the organization in accordance with established standards. Performance encompasses not only the final output but also the processes, behaviors, and contributions of employees in supporting the attainment of organizational goals. This perspective aligns with the views of (Kaswan & Akhyadi, 2017) and (Busro, 2018), who emphasize that performance reflects an employee's abilities, skills, and work behaviors over a specific period. (Arisanti et al., 2019) and (Putri, 2020) further assert that performance can be measured through the quality and quantity of work results, which serve as critical indicators for assessing organizational effectiveness and form the basis for managerial decision-making. In the context of the State Civil Apparatus (ASN), performance assessments are also grounded in legal provisions, as stipulated in Government Regulation Number 30 of 2019, which mandates that performance evaluations be conducted objectively, measurably, and transparently to support career development and enhance employee professionalism.

Employee performance is influenced by various factors, both individual and organizational. One significant factor is work-related stress, which arises when job demands exceed an individual's capacity, resulting in decreased motivation and concentration (Sari & Sutanto, 2021). Additionally, organizational change plays a crucial role, especially when it is not accompanied by effective communication and employee engagement, potentially leading to resistance and job uncertainty (Sholihatin et al., 2023). Adaptive leadership also contributes to employee success in navigating the dynamics of organizational change, as adaptive leaders provide direction, support, and motivation tailored to the conditions faced (Cahyani, 2026). Moreover, role clarity enhances performance by fostering a clear understanding of duties and responsibilities, thereby reducing role conflict and increasing focus and effectiveness (Hadi & Supriadi, 2025).

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Employee performance measurement, particularly for State Civil Apparatus, generally refers to government regulations that categorize performance into two main components: Employee Performance Targets (SKP) and work behavior. SKP encompasses aspects such as quantity, quality, timeliness, and cost in task execution, while work behavior includes service orientation, integrity, discipline, cooperation, and leadership (PP No. 46 of 2011). These indicators align with the performance concepts proposed by (Adekiya, 2024) and (Vuong & Nguyen, 2022), which emphasize the importance of quality work outcomes, punctuality, and responsibility in task completion. Therefore, this study adopts performance indicators based on Government Regulation No. 46 of 2011, as they are considered most relevant to the characteristics of the research subject, namely the State Civil Apparatus, and effectively describe employee performance comprehensively and contextually.

2.2. Work Stress

Job stress is a psychological condition that arises when an individual perceives an imbalance between job demands and their abilities, knowledge, and resources. This condition can affect an employee's emotional, cognitive, and physical well-being, thereby impacting their comfort and effectiveness at work. (Alfarol & Bahwiyanti, 2023) and (Ghani & Muttaqiyathun, 2023) define job stress as an individual's response to perceived excessive and unpleasant pressures in the work environment. This perspective is supported by (Heryanda, 2019) and (Usman & Latief, 2022), who emphasize that job stress is closely linked to feelings of pressure, anxiety, and work-related physical disorders. However, (Efendi et al., 2022) argue that stress is not always negative; it can, to some extent, serve as a motivator when managed with organizational support and appropriate stress management strategies.

Employee work stress levels are influenced by various organizational factors, including organizational change, adaptive leadership, and role clarity. Organizational changes such as restructuring, the implementation of new technologies, and modifications to work systems often create uncertainty and anxiety, especially when not accompanied by adequate communication and employee engagement (Sholihatin et al., 2023). In these situations, adaptive leadership plays a crucial role in reducing work stress by providing clear direction, emotional support, and the flexibility to adjust leadership styles according to the conditions employees face (Guntoro, 2020). Furthermore, role clarity is essential because unclear tasks and responsibilities can trigger role conflict and increase psychological stress, whereas a clear understanding of roles can alleviate stress caused by work ambiguity (Badu & Djafri, 2017). Job stress is typically measured using various indicators that reflect individual demands and organizational conditions. (Ghani & Muttaqiyathun, 2023) proposed job stress indicators encompassing task demands, role demands, interpersonal demands, organizational structure, and organizational leadership. These indicators align with the findings of (Maulana, 2022), who emphasized workload, time pressure, role conflict, and social support, as well as (Efendi et al., 2022), who incorporated aspects of the work environment and job control. This study adopts the job stress indicators from the (Ghani & Muttaqiyathun, 2023) model because it is considered comprehensive, relevant to the modern organizational context, and capable of thoroughly describing job stress from individual, social, and organizational structural perspectives.

2.3 Organizational Change

Organizational change is an adaptive process undertaken by organizations in response to the continuously evolving dynamics of their internal and external environments. (Şendrea & Grecea, 2025) define organizational change as an adjustment effort involving strategy, structure, technology, and human resource management to ensure the organization remains relevant and competitive. This perspective aligns with (Boonstra, 2013), who emphasize that organizational change is not merely technical but also encompasses systems, values, culture, and individual behavior within the organization, aiming to enhance effectiveness and sustainability. (Robbins & Judge, 2023) adds that an organization's ability to survive largely depends on its capacity to respond and adapt to environmental changes, making change fundamentally focused on improving the performance and work behavior of its members. Organizational change can be classified into several primary categories. (Robbins & Judge, 2023) identifies four main types: structural, technological, physical, and individual changes. Structural change involves modifications to authority relationships, coordination mechanisms, job design, and decision-making systems, including centralization and decentralization. Technological change pertains to the adoption of new work methods, automation, and information technology, with success largely dependent on user acceptance of the technology's benefits and convenience. Physical changes refer to the arrangement of workspaces, layouts, and environmental conditions that enhance employee comfort and safety. Individual change focuses on adjusting employees' attitudes, skills, perceptions, and behaviors to enable them to work more effectively in response to organizational demands. To minimize the risk of change failure, a systematic change management model is essential. Kotter (2008) proposed the Eight-Step Model of Change, which emphasizes the importance of creating a sense of urgency, forming a strong coalition, developing and communicating a clear vision for change, empowering employees, and generating short-term wins to drive momentum. Additionally, change must be consolidated and institutionalized to become an integral part of the organizational culture. Regarding organizational change indicators, the Ministry of Education and Culture (2020) categorizes change into aspects such as academic autonomy, independent human resource management, active governance roles, and decentralized resource management. These indicators reflect structural and managerial changes designed to enhance organizational flexibility, accountability, and sustainable performance.

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2.4. Adaptive Leadership

Adaptive leadership is an approach that emphasizes a leader's ability to navigate change, complexity, and uncertainty within an organizational environment. Adaptive leaders not only respond to change but also proactively foster learning, innovation, and collaboration within their teams. According to (Northouse, 2013), adaptive leadership centers on a leader's capacity to guide an organization through rapid change by motivating, empowering, and supporting team members as they confront dynamic challenges. In this context, the leader serves both as a director and a facilitator, helping the organization maintain effectiveness amid change. Furthermore, adaptive leadership is understood as a leader's ability to manage uncertainty and foster organizational resilience through flexibility and innovation. (Naim, 2024) explains that adaptive leadership emphasizes the importance of collaboration, continuous learning, and openness to new ideas when facing complex challenges. This perspective is reinforced by (Yukl & Gardner, 2020), who asserts that adaptive leaders must recognize new challenges, communicate effectively, and make strategic decisions that support organizational sustainability. Thus, adaptive leadership encompasses not only technical managerial skills but also interpersonal aspects and sustainable change management.

Adaptive leadership is assessed through various indicators that reflect a leader's ability to respond effectively to organizational dynamics. (Safitri & Tanujaya, 2024) identified key indicators of adaptive leadership, including flexibility, analytical skills, communication skills, leadership strength, collaboration, and problem-solving abilities. These indicators align with those proposed by (Nöthel et al., 2023), who additionally emphasized trust-building, conflict management, team empowerment, and the capacity to manage uncertainty. This study adopted the indicators from (Safitri & Tanujaya, 2024) because they are considered relevant and comprehensive for describing adaptive leadership in modern organizations, as well as suitable for evaluating leaders' roles in managing change and promoting sustainable organizational performance.

2.5. Role Clarity

Role clarity refers to an employee's understanding of the duties, responsibilities, authority, and performance expectations associated with their role within the organization. Employees with clear roles know exactly what is expected of them, how their work contributes to organizational goals, and the criteria used to evaluate their performance. According to JRG Partners (2024), role clarity promotes alignment between individual roles and overall organizational objectives, thereby minimizing confusion and enhancing task effectiveness.

In addition to enhancing work effectiveness, role clarity is essential for minimizing the potential for role conflict and work-related stress. When tasks and responsibilities are not clearly defined, employees often experience uncertainty, which can result in psychological stress and reduced performance. (Meidilisa & Lukito, 2020) explain that role clarity involves understanding job descriptions, ensuring the suitability of the position for assigned tasks, and receiving clear instructions from supervisors. This clarity enables employees to work with greater focus, direction, and alignment with organizational expectations.

Role clarity can be measured through several key indicators that reflect the extent to which employees understand and effectively perform their roles. (Meidilisa & Lukito, 2020) proposed indicators of role clarity, including the clarity of job descriptions, the appropriateness of tasks assigned to the position, understanding of responsibilities, consistency of instructions from supervisors, and employee involvement in task determination. These indicators offer a comprehensive overview of employees' work role conditions and are particularly relevant for organizational research, especially in examining the relationship between role clarity, job stress, and employee performance.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

In this study, the population consisted of all Education Personnel with Civil Servant status at Syiah Kuala University, totaling 578 individuals. A census technique was employed, using the entire ASN Tendik population at Syiah Kuala University as the research sample. This approach ensures that the research results are more comprehensive and accurately reflect the actual conditions. To discuss the research, the researcher used previously collected data analysis tools. The data analysis in this study used the SEM method using AMOS.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Hypothesis Testing

The testing of the research hypothesis is as in Table 1 below.

Table 1 Regression Weight Structural Equational Model

			Standardized	SE	CR	P	R Square
Work Stress	<---	Organizational Change	-.304	.080	-2.895	.017	
Work Stress	<---	Adaptive Leadership	-.367	.088	-3.250	***	0.751
Work Stress	<---	Role Clarity	-.340	.070	-3.047	***	
Performance Employee	<---	Organizational Change	.278	.101	2.704	.011	0.818

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		Standardized	SE	CR	P	R Square
Performance Employee	<--- Adaptive Leadership	.223	.118	2.372	.023	
Performance Employee	<--- Role Clarity	.170	.086	2.011	.048	
Performance Employee	<--- Work Stress	-.493	.093	4.354	***	

Source: Processed Primary Data, (2025)

4.1.1. Direct Hypothesis Testing

The research results show that organizational and leadership factors play a significant role in influencing employee job stress levels. Organizational change was shown to have a significant negative effect on job stress, indicating that well-planned and managed change can reduce employee stress levels. These findings confirm that a clear, structured, and communicative change process can help employees adapt, thereby reducing the psychological stress that arises from job uncertainty.

In addition to organizational change, adaptive leadership also plays a significant role in reducing employee work stress. Flexible, responsive leadership, which adapts to organizational dynamics, has been shown to significantly reduce work stress levels. This demonstrates that adaptive leaders are able to provide direction, support, and a sense of security to employees in the face of ever-changing and evolving work demands.

Role clarity is also a significant factor influencing employee job stress. Analysis shows that the clearer the tasks, responsibilities, and performance expectations employees receive, the lower their perceived stress levels. Role clarity helps employees focus on their work, avoids role conflict, and reduces uncertainty that can potentially lead to psychological distress.

Furthermore, the research findings confirm that organizational change, adaptive leadership, and role clarity significantly influence employee performance, both directly and through job stress. Job stress has been shown to have a strong negative impact on performance, indicating that increased stress will decrease employee productivity. Therefore, managing organizational change, strengthening adaptive leadership, and improving role clarity are important strategies for reducing job stress and sustainably improving employee performance.

4.1.2. Testing the Mediation Hypothesis

The results of the mediation effect test indicate that job stress plays a significant role in bridging the relationship between organizational change and employee performance. Based on the Sobel test results, a statistical value of 3.115 was obtained with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.001$, indicating that job stress acts as a significant mediating variable. This finding indicates that organizational change not only directly affects employee performance but also indirectly through decreasing or increasing levels of job stress.

Furthermore, the results of the mediation test on the relationship between adaptive leadership and employee performance also showed a significant role of job stress as an intervening variable. The Sobel test value of 3.238 with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.001$ confirmed that job stress partially mediated the relationship. This means that adaptive leadership can improve employee performance both directly and through work stress management mechanisms, making the role of leaders crucial in creating conducive and performance-oriented work conditions.

Similar results were found regarding the effect of role clarity on employee performance through job stress. A Sobel test value of 3.474 with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.000$ indicates that job stress acts as a significant mediator. Partial mediation in this relationship indicates that role clarity contributes directly to improved employee performance, while also reducing job stress levels arising from uncertainty about tasks and responsibilities.

Overall, the findings of this study confirm that job stress is an important psychological mechanism in explaining how organizational change, adaptive leadership, and role clarity affect employee performance. The partial mediation of job stress suggests that efforts to improve employee performance depend not only on structural and leadership aspects but also on the organization's ability to effectively manage job stress. Therefore, organizational strategies that focus on managing change, strengthening adaptive leadership, and improving role clarity will have optimal impact when accompanied by job stress management policies.

4.2. DISCUSSION

Organizational change has been shown to affect employee stress levels at work. Change processes that involve adjustments to structures, tasks, and work systems often create uncertainty and new demands, which can increase employees' psychological stress. If change is not managed effectively, it can potentially lead to burnout, impaired well-being, and reduced work readiness. Therefore, planned and communicative change management is essential for minimizing work-related stress.

In addition to driving organizational change, adaptive leadership plays a crucial role in mitigating work-related stress. Leaders who adjust their leadership style to align with organizational dynamics can offer employees a sense of security, emotional support, and clear direction. This approach helps employees manage work demands more effectively, thereby reducing stress levels. Consequently, adaptive leadership acts as a psychological buffer in evolving work environments.

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Role clarity has been demonstrated to be a critical factor in reducing employee work-related stress. Unclear roles and responsibilities often lead to confusion and role conflict, which ultimately increase work stress. Conversely, a clear understanding of roles enables employees to work more purposefully, reduces uncertainty, and mitigates potential stress. This confirms that role clarity is a fundamental aspect of human resource management.

The research also demonstrates that organizational change significantly impacts employee performance. Effectively designed and implemented changes can enhance efficiency, commitment, and overall work performance. However, if changes are not supported by appropriate task allocation and adequate support, employee performance may decline. Therefore, the success of organizational change largely depends on management's ability to align work structures and roles with employee capabilities.

Adaptive leadership has been shown to positively impact employee performance. Adaptive leaders encourage employee readiness for change, enhance work engagement, and foster the development of adaptive skills. This approach enables employees to maintain productivity even in dynamic work environments. Therefore, adaptive leadership is a strategic factor in sustainably improving employee performance.

Role clarity directly impacts employee performance. Employees who clearly understand their duties, authorities, and responsibilities tend to work more effectively and efficiently. It helps reduce errors, improve focus, and strengthen individual accountability. This demonstrates that role clarity is a crucial prerequisite for achieving optimal performance.

Work-related stress has been shown to negatively affect employee performance. Excessive stress can diminish concentration, motivation, and work quality, as well as adversely impact employee health. While moderate levels of stress can be motivating, unmanaged stress becomes a significant barrier to organizational success. Therefore, managing work stress should be a primary concern for management.

Furthermore, the results of the mediation test indicate that job stress partially mediates the relationship between organizational change, adaptive leadership, role clarity, and employee performance. This finding confirms that these three factors influence performance not only directly but also indirectly through the psychological mechanism of job stress. Therefore, efforts to improve employee performance will be more effective if organizations focus not only on structural and leadership aspects but also on systematically managing job stress.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the research findings, it can be concluded that employee performance, work stress levels, organizational change, adaptive leadership, and role clarity at Syiah Kuala University are all within favorable ranges. This suggests that the overall organizational and human resource management has been quite effective, although certain factors still influence employee well-being and performance.

Test results indicate that organizational change, adaptive leadership, and role clarity directly influence employee job stress. Poorly managed organizational change, ineffective leadership, and role ambiguity can increase job stress. Conversely, well-managed change, responsive leadership, and clear role definitions can reduce employee stress levels.

In addition to influencing work stress, organizational change, adaptive leadership, and role clarity have been shown to directly affect employee performance. Employees perform better when the organization effectively adapts to change, leaders provide appropriate guidance and support, and work roles are clearly defined. Conversely, work stress significantly impacts employee performance, with increased stress generally leading to decreased performance.

Furthermore, job stress acts as a partial mediating variable in the relationship between organizational change, adaptive leadership, and role clarity on employee performance. These findings indicate that these three factors influence performance both directly and indirectly through job stress. Therefore, improving employee performance at Syiah Kuala University requires an integrated approach that includes change management, strengthening adaptive leadership, clarifying roles, and managing job stress.

5.2 SUGGESTIONS

1. The organizational change variable achieved the lowest average score of 3.42. This should serve as a focus for organizations to increase the active involvement of the supervisory board, board of trustees, and academic senate in formulating strategic policies. Organizations need to strengthen coordination mechanisms, increase transparency in decision-making, and encourage stronger collaboration between strategic organs to optimize policy formulation.
2. The adaptive leadership variable showed the lowest average score of 3.66 for the indicator of a leader's ability to analyze problems comprehensively before making a decision. This should be a concern for organizations, requiring leaders to receive training focused on developing analytical skills, data-driven decision-making, and problem-solving. Strengthening a culture of discussion and considering multiple perspectives can also help leaders make more informed decisions.
3. The role clarity variable achieved the lowest average score of 3.26, indicating that some employees do not yet clearly understand their job descriptions and responsibilities. This issue should be addressed by organizations, encouraging them to

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- more structuredly disseminate job descriptions, provide easily accessible task documents, and conduct regular briefings between superiors and subordinates. Efforts to realign tasks with positions are also necessary to avoid role ambiguity.
4. The work stress variable had the lowest average score of 2.60 for the leadership style indicator, which was assessed as still tending towards authoritarianism. This should be a concern for organizations to encourage leaders to adopt a more supportive, participatory, and communicative leadership style. Leadership training, improving interpersonal skills, and creating a more open work environment can help reduce the potential for work stress caused by less flexible leadership styles.
 5. The employee performance variable showed the lowest average score of 3.50 for the indicator related to employee actions that align with organizational values, norms, and ethics. This should be a focus for organizations to strengthen the internalization of work culture through the socialization of organizational values, work ethics training, and leadership role models. Furthermore, the consistent implementation of a reward and consequence system can help improve employee compliance with applicable values and ethics.

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